

Conductometric and Spectrophotometric Study of Thallium (I) Complexes of α -Alanine and β -Alanine

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Spectrophotometric and conductometric measurements reveal that thallium(I) forms 1 : 1 complex with α -alanine and β -alanine. The dissociation constants of these complexes, applying Job's method to conductance and optical density, are calculated to be about 3.2×10^{-2} and 9.2×10^{-2} for thallos- α -alaninate and thallos- β -alaninate respectively at 28°.

α - and β -amino acids have long been known to form complexes with many metal ions^{1,2}. Investigations on the complexes formed by thallos ion with α - and β -alanine are reported in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

E. Merck make of thallos nitrate and B.D.H. samples of α -alanine and β -alanine were used. Sodium salts of these acids were employed as thallos complexes are more stable in alkaline medium. All solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

Conductance measurements were done by "Doran" conductivity bridge with 1000 cycle WTW Oscillator and dip type conductivity cell. Optical densities were measured by "Beckmann model DU quartz spectrophotometer" using 5 mm thick absorption cells. All the measurements were done at a temperature of 28°.

Stoichiometry : Conductivity measurements were employed to monovariation method³ and Job's⁴ continuous variation method for establishing the composition of the complexes. $M/30$, $M/40$ and $M/60$ equimolar solutions were used. By both the methods formation of 1 : 1 complexes have been inferred.

The composition of the complexes were further confirmed by Job's⁴ method applying to optical density measurements to $M/20$ equimolar solutions at wave lengths 250, 255 and 260 m μ .

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Dissociation Constant: The dissociation constant of both the complexes were calculated by applying Job's method to non-equimolar solutions using conductivity and optical density as index properties. For this calculation the formula

$$K = \frac{c[(p+1)x-1]^2}{(p-1)(1-2x)}$$

was used. The results are comprised in the table below

TABLE 1

Dissociation constants by conductivity and optical density measurements

Index Property	Complex	c	p	x	K
Conductivity	Thalious-	M/60	1.5	0.48	3.3×10^{-2}
	α -alaninate	M/60	2.0	0.46	3.0×10^{-2}
	Thalious-	M/60	1.5	0.49	8.4×10^{-2}
	β -alaninate	M/80	2.0	0.485	8.6×10^{-2}
Optical density	Thalious-	M/50	2.5	0.44	3.2×10^{-2}
	α -alaninate				
	Thalious-	M/50	2.5	0.47	9.2×10^{-2}
	β -alaninate				

The dissociation constants calculated by conductivity as well as optical density measurements show fair agreement with each other.

Conductivity as well as optical density measurements reveal that thallium (I) forms 1 : 1 complex both with α -alanine and β -alanine.

From the instability data it is observed that thalious- α -alaninate is much more stable than thalious- β -alaninate. The reason for this seems to be the probable formation of a five membered ring by thalious- α -alaninate and a six membered ring by thalious- β -alaninate. Ley⁵ and Kirson and Borsily⁶ have also found that copper complex of α -alanine is much more stable than that of β -alanine.

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